

ISW

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D6.4 Open source software for rule-based data sharing

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Quality assurance

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List of abbreviations

ISW	In Silico World
WP	Work Package
HPC	High Performance Computing
MEE	Model Execution Environment
UPS	Uninterruptible Power Supply
API	Application Programming Interface
DMT	Deep Modelling Track
DAT	Deep Accreditation Track
ATMP	Advanced Therapy Medicinal Products
FAME	Fractional flow reserve versus Angiography for Multivessel Evaluation trial
FEM	Finite Element Method
DOI	Digital Object Identifier

1. Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable is to report on the data sharing and publishing framework that has been developed in the context of WP6 of the ISW project, to ensure that research data is coherently managed.

The data management tools, focus of this report, include platforms for the upload of input data to HPC resources, automatic marshalling of such data on HPC clusters, referencing data items for processing and downloading by end users, staging out output data to external repositories where they can be accessed by collaborating scientists, and tools for publishing and referencing research data in scientific publications and otherwise. Additionally, the report describes the data-sharing practices and strategies for community involvement.

This document builds on previous documentation developed in WP6; particularly Deliverable 6.2 - Scalability strategies report, which details the ISW research workflows and means by which they are submitted to, and processed by, the available computational infrastructure. D6.2 also contains a description of the Model Execution Environment (MEE) (1), which is used to manage computational workflows in the context of ISW. This report describes the extension of the MEE tool with features required for advanced data-sharing capabilities, as well as the development of the infrastructure that supports these capabilities and enables data dissemination.

The developed instruments are compliant with Open Science principles and FAIR data management guidelines, aiming to benefit the global scientific community and support research within the In Silico World project.

2. Managing research data in In Silico World

In the context of In Silico World project, a lot of research data are produced and analysed. Hence, they have to be stored securely and shared amongst research team members. At the end of the research process, results need to be aggregated and published to support Open Science. Considering the trends in modern scientific community, open-source solutions for data storage and sharing are preferred.

2.1. Internal Storage Solutions

For internal sharing of research data, secure solutions with restricted access are essential. An example of such solutions, used in the project, is the SharePoint (2) storage systems of In Silico World member institutions. These systems are utilized as temporary storage for research data during the processing stage, before they are ready for publication. This approach is effective for internal data sharing, as it limits access to members of specific institutions and selected partners.

An example is the UNIBO SharePoint (3), where only researchers from the University of Bologna and ISW consortium members have access. It is used for storing project documentation and resources. Another solution in use is Sano's primary SharePoint (4) storage, which is also dedicated to internal storage and sharing. It is accessible to Sano's researchers and selected partners. For example, the DPValid (5) dataset was transferred there after the research process around it was completed, to be prepared for publication on an open access platform.

2.2. Open access data publication

There are solutions for external sharing and publication of research data, including open-source data-sharing repositories like Zenodo (6) and Dataverse (7). These repositories support advanced data management, offering secure shared storage with authorized access. After data are uploaded, it can be published, provided it does not contain personal information or malicious content, which is thoroughly reviewed by administrators.

When published, a persistent identifier – such as a Digital Object Identifier (8) – is registered and assigned to the data. A DOI is globally indexed and enables citation in publications, articles, and other research works. It serves as a unique identifier linked to the metadata, which ensures that even if the original data are moved, updated, or deleted, the DOI remains valid. This ensures that citation mechanisms remain intact, and the dataset or file continues to be trackable globally.

Data repositories support the FAIR principles—Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (9). Sticking to these principles ensures that data can be easily utilized by both humans and computers. Findability is achieved through machine-readable metadata, which is associated with a persistent identifier (such as a DOI) and indexed in searchable resources like public registries. For example, a dataset with a DOI can be directly indexed via search engines or repository platforms. Accessibility is ensured by providing data through open and free protocols such as HTTPS, with the option for authentication and authorization procedures when required. Importantly, even if the data become unavailable, the metadata remains accessible, ensuring long-term references to the dataset. Interoperability is facilitated by the use of standardized metadata formats, such as JSON or XML, FAIR-compliant vocabularies, and metadata schemas like Dublin Core or DataCite, enabling integration with different data sharing platforms. Reusability is supported by rich, community-standard metadata, along with a clear and accessible licensing framework, such as Creative Commons licenses. This ensures researchers can understand, validate, and build upon the data.

By adhering to these principles, data repositories enable DOI registration to ensure findability and accessibility, while usage of standard metadata formats enhances interoperability with other systems. Additionally, the structured nature of the repositories facilitates data reuse. This alignment with FAIR principles is key to advancing Open Science and promoting transparency, collaboration, and the long-term usability of research data.

2.2.1. Zenodo

Zenodo is an open repository built and operated by CERN and OpenAIRE (10). It stores research outputs from EU-funded projects, including In Silico World. Zenodo is organized into communities and uploads, which can be associated with communities or published independently. Every user can create a community and an upload.

In Zenodo, In Silico World has a dedicated community titled “Open Access Resources of the In Silico World H2020 project” (11), where research datasets and important project documents are publicly accessible. When a resource is selected for publication within this community, a curation process is performed to ensure the resource will be published according to the FAIR principles. The In Silico World community includes research datasets, published according to In Silico World Data Management Plan, such as ValveValid (12), DPValid (reduced version) (5), MSValid (13), TBValid (14), StentValid (15) and HFValid (16). Additionally, project deliverables and reports, like D9.2 (17) and D9.3 (18), are published there.

2.2.2. Dataverse

An analogous open-source solution is The Dataverse Project, one of the primary multidisciplinary data-sharing platforms. Dataverse is developed by the Dataverse team at the Institute for Quantitative Social Science at Harvard University. Since anyone can set up an instance, there are currently 125 registered instances worldwide. Each instance has a structure consisting of a root dataverse, which can nest multiple sub-dataverses. These sub-dataverses can, in turn, nest additional sub-dataverses or datasets, which store data files.

Sano Centre for Computational Medicine manages its own instance, called Sano Dataverse (the production instance (19) is being configured, the test instance (20) is online), to meet the needs of In Silico World project members, partners from other projects, and internal researchers. Each team and partner have their own sub-dataverse within the instance. Logging in and registration are handled via Microsoft Entra ID Single Sign-On system (21), and after registration, the administrator assigns permissions to upload data within the selected sub-dataverse, ensuring that only verified users can contribute. Additionally, all data are thoroughly reviewed before publishing to ensure accurate metadata and to prevent malicious content. Each dataset is required to include a README file with a description of the data. To be published, all files within the dataset must be in open-access formats. If the data cannot be presented in these formats, the README file should include a description of the software needed to open the file.

Sano Dataverse is in the process of joining the RODBUK Cracow Open Research Data Repository (22). This project is managed by the Kraków Library Group and includes instances from Kraków universities and research institutions. All data published on RODBUK are stored at ACC Cyfronet (23), protected by specific security and backup measures. RODBUK complies with the OpenAIRE guidelines and follows the FAIR Principles. Datasets from all RODBUK members are aggregated on its main page, giving them more visibility and increasing their chances of being recognized and cited. More information on RODBUK and its guidelines can be found in the section 4.4.

3. Use of research data in ISW computational workflows

The MEE platform, used in the In Silico World project, facilitates the execution of computational models by performing simulations on HPC infrastructure. Data are stored directly on this infrastructure, and results are generated on HPC storage as well. Previously, MEE integrated with the PLGData tool (24) to provide access to users’ folders and files within the PL-Grid infrastructure. This

tool relied on the GridFTP protocol (25), developed 25 years ago, which no longer meets the modern standards required by a platform like MEE. Consequently, a new storage solution was necessary—one capable of securely and efficiently managing and transferring large data volumes. This led to the development of new integrations.

3.1. Cloud storage

The Model Execution Environment platform utilizes integration with Amazon AWS S3 storage (26). It serves as storage for the research data uploaded to the platform and for derived results. Integration is performed at the level of virtual organizations in MEE. Each organization is connected to an S3 storage bucket, which serves as the organizational storage, where all patient data, pipeline inputs and outputs, and artifacts are stored. By default, each bucket has 5GB of storage, but this can be extended by the application administrator if sufficient justification is provided.

3.2. MEE integration with data repositories

Although S3 storage can be connected and used seamlessly, it is a costly service. As a result, bucket memory is limited, which restricts the number of files that can be stored within an organization—this may be a limitation for large-scale simulations. A potential solution is to use data-sharing repositories to store input datasets for models and simulation results. Research data can be published or stored privately there, with access provided to the entire research group or only to selected individuals. Examples of such repositories used in the In Silico World project, like Zenodo and Dataverse, are described in Section 2.2.

However, storing data in these external repositories still requires S3 as an intermediary. To upload data to MEE, users must first download it from the repository to their own machine, upload it to S3 storage, and then transfer it to the HPC infrastructure. The same applies to results generated after simulations—they are uploaded to S3, from where users can manually transfer them to a data-sharing repository. This highlights the need for direct integration between HPC and data-sharing repositories. MEE supports this integration, allowing seamless, automatic data flow between the data repository instance and the HPC infrastructure.

Figure 1: MEE integration with data repositories

This process is handled via API calls made by the HPC during script execution. The code responsible for making these calls is inserted using tags, which are interpolated into the script and replaced with the corresponding instructions during the simulation submission stage.

3.2.1. Configuration

To enable HPC to send requests to the API of a desired repository and its specific instance, some configuration within MEE at the virtual organization level is needed. Additionally, requests require authorization, so an access token must be added to the user's membership associated with the integrated organization.

Figure 2: MEE access delineation system structure

To configure the integration setup for an organization, its administrator must select the type of repository to integrate with – either Dataverse or Zenodo. The administrator must then provide the URL of the corresponding instance to be integrated with. The selected repository type allows for verification that correct tags are inserted into the script. The URL, in turn, is inserted into the API requests to address the specified instance.

Data repository configuration

The data repository integration allow your organization to use liquid tags for accessing remote resources from supported repositories. Users will be able to access files and datasets with the API token, if present in user profile. More details can be found in help section: [Data Repository Manual](#)

Enable data repository integration

Data Repository Type

dataverse ✓ ▾

dataverse

zenodo

Data repository url *

https://dataverse.sano.science/ ✓

Figure 3: Example data repository configuration in the organization

Once the data repository configuration is enabled and set up within the organization, all users in it can set up a personal access token for their membership, associated with this organization. This can be done in the user’s profile within the corresponding organization.

Figure 4: Example personal access token configuration for the user's membership

The personal access token is an API token from the data repository, that can be obtained from the user profile on any instance of either Zenodo or Dataverse. It is required for API calls that require authorization, such as downloading an unpublished file or dataset or uploading a file to an unpublished dataset. By attaching this token to such requests, the data repository will verify whether the account associated with the token has access to the requested unpublished or restricted data and will return it accordingly.

3.2.2. Liquid tags

Liquid (27) is a Ruby template engine that allows for the detection and replacement of the integration tags mentioned above in the script. These tags are identified by their syntax and replaced with API calls using the curl (28) tool, with additional logic and error handling applied underneath. To use the integration, users must insert the desired tags into their script and provide parameters for them, which will affect the request options.

There are three types of tags for each repository type: two for staging data into the computation environment and one for staging data out to the repository. The tags accept different arguments depending on the repository type, due to differences in the APIs of Zenodo and Dataverse. The tags for Dataverse include:

- `{% dataverse_file_stage_in persistentID target %}` – allows for staging in a file from the Dataverse instance to the HPC infrastructure:
 - *persistentID* – the persistent identifier of the file on the instance;
 - *target* (optional) – an optional name for the file to be saved with on the HPC infrastructure. If not provided, the file retains its original name from the instance;
- `{% dataverse_dataset_stage_in persistentID target %}` – allows for staging in a dataset from the Dataverse instance to the HPC infrastructure:
 - *persistentID* – the persistent identifier of the dataset on the instance (usually in DOI format);
 - *target* (optional) – an optional name for the .zip archive file where the dataset content will be stored after download. If not provided, the archive is unpacked in `$SCRATCHDIR`, and the dataset content is stored in its original format, preserving the directory structure of the dataset;

- `{% dataverse_file_stage_out filePath persistentID metadata %}` – allows for staging out a file from the HPC infrastructure to a specific dataset on the Dataverse instance
 - `filePath` – the path to the file that needs to be uploaded from the HPC infrastructure;
 - `persistentID` – the persistent identifier of the dataset to which the file will be uploaded;
 - `metadata` (optional) – a set of metadata for the file in JSON format which will be displayed on the instance (e.x. relative path in the dataset, category labels, restriction);

The tags for Zenodo include:

- `{% zenodo_file_stage_in recordID filename target %}` – allows for staging in a file from the Zenodo instance to the HPC infrastructure:
 - `recordID` – the persistent identifier of the record where the desired file is situated on the instance;
 - `filename` – name of the file in the record;
 - `target` (optional) - an optional name for the file to be saved with on the HPC infrastructure. If not provided, the file retains its original name from the instance;
- `{% zenodo_dataset_stage_in recordID target %}` – allows for staging in a record from the Zenodo instance to the HPC infrastructure:
 - `recordID` – the persistent identifier of the record (dataset) on the instance in DOI format;
 - `target` (optional) – an optional name for the .zip archive file where the dataset content will be stored after download. If not provided, the archive is unpacked in `$$SCRATCHDIR`, and the dataset content is stored in its original format, preserving the directory structure of the dataset;
- `{% zenodo_file_stage_out filePath depositID %}` – allows for staging out a file from the HPC infrastructure to a specific deposit on the Zenodo instance:
 - `filePath` – the path to the file that needs to be uploaded from the HPC infrastructure;
 - `persistentID` – the persistent identifier of the dataset to which the file will be uploaded;

The use of tags in scripts requires the appropriate data repository configuration to be set up within the organization and a token set up in the membership. If this configuration is missing or if the repository type in the configuration does not match the tags in the script, any computation containing these tags will be blocked. In such cases, the user will receive a warning indicating the need to set up or adjust the data repository configuration.

A detailed guide on configuration and tag usage can be found in the MEE help section. It describes usage of the available parameters for the tags and the essential configuration. Additional information on data repositories and the APIs used for integration is available in the repositories’ documentation: the Dataverse Documentation (29) provides comprehensive information about Dataverse, while Zenodo offers resources in Zenodo Help (30) for general usage and Zenodo Developers (31) for development and API integration purposes.

Figure 5: Help section including Data repository guide in MEE

3.2.3. Example usage

First, a proper configuration within the virtual organization in MEE is necessary to utilize integration. An example demonstrational setup, previously shown in Figure 3, was performed by the organization’s administrator to integrate it with the Sano Dataverse instance.

Next, a personal access token must be obtained from the user’s account in the Sano Dataverse and entered as shown in Figure 4.

Account - Sano Dataverse

Figure 6: API token in the user profile on the Sano Dataverse

Once all configurations are correctly completed, a script can be modified with tags for downloading and uploading data from the data repository. For example, the UISS-COVID19 simulation model, integrated with Dataverse, consists of two scripts. The first script (Figure 7) downloads an input data file using a given DOI from Dataverse, runs a simulation with it, and stages all the results to MEE.

```

echo Download specified single file from dataverse
echo -----START-----
file doi={% value of file doi %}
{% dataverse_file_stage_in $file_doi %}
echo -----END-----

echo Copying input datafile
if [ -f $SCRATCHDIR/datafile* ]
then
  cp -f "$(ls $SCRATCHDIR/datafile*)" $TMPDIR
  mv "$(ls $TMPDIR/datafile*)" $TMPDIR/input
fi

pwd

echo Giving permission
chmod +x uiss-covid19/uiss_ELF_64-bit_LSB

## Running simulation
echo Simulation started
singularity exec --home $TMPDIR /$PLG_GROUPS_STORAGE/plggisw/uiss_ubuntu_gsl.sif ./
uiss-covid19/uiss_ELF_64-bit_LSB -f input

```

Figure 7: Part of the first script of the integrated with Dataverse UISS-COVID19 model

The second part of the model involves obtaining the simulation outputs, generating plots, and uploading these plots to a Dataverse dataset, using metadata to organize them into subdirectories and assigning them a “Plot” category for better recognition and organization (Figure 8).

```

## Get the output files from simulation
{% stage_in outputs %}
mkdir outputs
tar -xvzf $SCRATCHDIR/*.tar.gz -C ./outputs

## Generating plots
echo Generating plots

TIMEARG={% value_of time_unit %}

cd outputs

gnuplot -c ../Antigen.plt 3 $TIMEARG 0
gnuplot -c ../cytokines.plt 3 $TIMEARG 0
gnuplot -c ../Ig.plt 3 $TIMEARG 0
gnuplot -c ../details.plt 3 $TIMEARG 0
echo Plots generated

dataset_doi={% value_of dataset_doi %}
subdir="{{ case_number }}_{{ pipeline_name }}"

## Staging out plots to dataverse.
for result_file in *.png
do
  if [ -f "$result_file" ]
  then
    {% dataverse_file_stage_out $result_file $dataset_doi {"directoryLabel":"'${subdir}'",
    "categories":["Plot"], "restrict":"false"} %}
  else
    continue
  fi
done

```

Figure 8: Part of the second script of the integrated with Dataverse UISS-COVID19 model

To run a simulation of this model on MEE, steps associated with these scripts must be created. Each step should be parametrized to allow users to specify the DOI of the input file and the dataset where output plots will be uploaded.

CPU
ARES
UISS-COVID19-run (uiss-covid19-run) Karol Zajac

Git

Repository: SanoISW/uiss-covid19
Slurm template: dataverse_demo_step1.job.bash.liquid

Parameters

- String Datafile DOI (script snippet {% value_of file_doi %})
- Model version Model version (script snippet {% value_of tag-or-branch %})
- Grant Grant (script snippet {% value_of grant %})

CPU
ARES
UISS-COVID19-plot (uiss-covid19-plot) Karol Zajac

Git

Repository: SanoISW/uiss-covid19
Slurm template: dataverse_demo_step2.job.bash.liquid

Required input data files

outputs (/\.*.tar.gz/)

Parameters

- Select Plot time scale (script snippet {% value_of time_unit %})
- Model version Model version (script snippet {% value_of tag-or-branch %})
- Grant Grant (script snippet {% value_of grant %})
- String Dataset DOI (script snippet {% value_of dataset_doi %})

Figure 9: MEE steps for integrated with Dataverse UISS-COVID19 model

These steps need to be organized into a flow to define their execution order.

UISS-COVID19

Steps

- UISS-COVID19-run
- UISS-COVID19-plot

Figure 10: MEE flow for integrated with Dataverse UISS-COVID19 model

A pipeline must then be constructed with the defined flow. To construct and run it, parameter values need to be specified. The first step of the flow requires the DOI of the UISS-COVID19 configuration file from the Sano Dataverse instance. This DOI can be found in the file's metadata on the instance (Figure 11).

datafile_test_mild_moderate

This file is part of "UISS-COVID19 Datafiles".

Version 3.1

File Citation

Zajac, Karol, 2023, "datafile_test_mild_moderate", *UISS-COVID19 Datafiles*, <https://doi.org/10.82726/sano/GE7NAW/HNBN7I>, Sano Dataverse, V3

Cite Data File ▾ Learn about [Data Citation Standards](#).

Figure 11: Mild Moderate UISS-COVID19 model configuration file on Sano Dataverse

The second step in the flow requires the DOI of the dataset where results will be uploaded. An empty dataset may be created on the instance specifically for this purpose (Figure 12).

UISS-COVID19 Study Results

Draft Unpublished

Zhyhulin, Taras, 2024, "UISS-COVID19 Study Results", <https://doi.org/10.82726/sano/HBSGP1>, Sano Dataverse, DRAFT VERSION ?

Cite Dataset ▾ Learn about [Data Citation Standards](#).

Description ?

Dataset contains the results from simulating the UISS-COVID19 model. Each subdirectory refers to the specific case or treatment and include graphics describing the state of immune system dynamics during the simulation process.

Subject ?

Medicine, Health and Life Sciences

Keyword ?

InSilicoWorld, COVID19, UISS

License/Data Use Agreement

Figure 12: Dataset on Sano Dataverse for UISS-COVID19 simulation results

Providing the DOIs of both the configuration file and dataset as parameter values enables the pipeline to execute.

UISS-COVID19-run

Datafile DOI *

doi:10.82726/sano/GE7NAW/HNBN71 ✓

The DOI of input datafile for simulation.

Model version *

dataverse_demo ✓ ↺

Grant *

plgisw3-cpu ▾

UISS-COVID19-plot

Plot time scale

days ✓ ▾

Model version *

dataverse_demo ✓ ↺

Grant *

plgisw3-cpu ▾

Dataset DOI *

doi:10.82726/sano/HBSGP1 ✓

Target dataset DOI for storing results.

Figure 13: Parameter values for the UISS-COVID19 simulation pipeline

After submission, some time is needed for queue processing and execution, but both steps are subsequently executed successfully (Figure 14), with the results visible on Sano Dataverse (Figure 15).

✓ UISS-COVID19-run
✓ UISS-COVID19-plot

UISS-COVID19-run finished successfully, results stored in the outputs directory.

Computation details

Start time 31 Oct 07:48

Site Ares

Revision 0c53339f8a806314cf612310e16db895d58e3fde

Execution time 00h 00m 46s

Outputs stdout, stderr

Status Finished

Saved parameter values

Grant plgplgisw2-cpu

Datafile doi:10.82726/sano/GE7NAW/HNBN7I
DOI

Model dataverse_demo
version

Figure 14: Successfully executed UISS-COVID19 simulation pipeline in MEE

☐ 1 to 10 of 22 Files

Edit Files ▾
 Download

☐		<p>Antigen.png testdasdasd_erwfdsf/ PNG Image - 6.2 KB Deposited May 31, 2024 MD5: 443...b13 </p> <p>Plot</p>	
☐		<p>B_det.png testdasdasd_erwfdsf/ PNG Image - 7.0 KB Deposited May 31, 2024 MD5: 64f...fe6 </p> <p>Plot</p>	
☐		<p>B_pop.png testdasdasd_erwfdsf/ PNG Image - 6.4 KB Deposited May 31, 2024 MD5: a9a...b33 </p> <p>Plot</p>	

Figure 15: Results of the UISS-COVID19 simulation pipeline uploaded on Sano Dataverse

By adding only a few lines to the scripts, the model was integrated with Dataverse. This integration allowed the direct download of the published input file and direct upload of the results, facilitating convenient display. No intermediate local storage was needed, the data transfer process was simplified, and MEE's S3 storage was not used, which is crucial for large-scale simulations requiring

numerous files and large data volumes. Additionally, the results are organized on a data-sharing platform with metadata, allowing them to be published immediately or shared with team members for further review and contribution.

4. Publishing and sharing outcomes of ISW research

After successful execution of the workflow, data appear on the instance in draft form. However, it still requires additional modifications and management to be published and to comply with FAIR principles. These procedures include specifying metadata, filtering data, and preparing descriptions and usage guidelines. General requirements include proper anonymization of the data, ensuring that individuals cannot be identified, or fully consent-cleared data; compliance with the law, meaning no infringement of intellectual property rights, exposure of confidential information, or publishing without required consent; and assurance that no malicious content, software, or offensive material is included.

4.1. Publishing on Zenodo

On Zenodo, metadata configuration is a required step before publication. Zenodo offers an extensive list of configurable metadata fields, but the following are mandatory:

- **DOI** - an existing one can be provided, or a new one can be generated;
- **the resource type** must be selected from a predefined list;
- **the record's title**, with the option to include more than one title;
- **the publication date**;
- **the creators**, with names specified or found by ORCID ID.

On Zenodo, a record must include at least one file, but no more than 100 files with a total size limit of 50 GB, although this quota may be increased. Additionally, a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license is selected by default, though it can be removed.

While Zenodo requires only minimal metadata to publish a record, it provides a wide range of metadata fields, allowing for detailed descriptions that enhance findability. Information about funding, alternate identifiers, related works, references, software, publishing details, conferences, and various domain-specific fields can be added to the standard list. The rich metadata capability is a significant advantage of the Zenodo repository.

After completing the metadata, the record can be published and assigned a DOI (if a previously registered DOI is not used). Whether the record is reviewed depends on the community's settings.

Review policy

Controls who can publish records directly without review.

 Review all submissions

All submissions to the community must be reviewed.

 Allow curators, managers and owners to publish without review

Submissions to the community by default requires review, but curators, managers and owners can publish directly without review.

 Allow all members to publish without review

Submissions to the community by default requires review, but all community members can publish directly without review.

Records submission policy

Controls who can submit records to the community.

 Open

All authenticated users can submit records to the community. If the community is restricted, then only members can submit records to it.

 Closed

Only members can submit records to the community.

Figure 16: Policy settings of the Zenodo community

Immediate publishing is possible if the publisher is a community member or has been invited to the community, and the review policy allows all members to publish freely. Otherwise, the record can only be submitted for review, after which curators, managers, or owners can approve it to make it public. After submission, a conversation associated with the record is opened, allowing the uploader to discuss any improvements or corrections needed before publication with the community administrators. The administrators can then either accept or decline the publication based on the record's value to the community and its metadata or content quality.

4.2. Publishing on Dataverse

The Dataverse Project is committed to using standards-compliant metadata to ensure that a Dataverse installation's metadata can be easily mapped to standard metadata schemas and exported into JSON format (or XML for tabular file metadata) for preservation and interoperability. A dataset in Dataverse contains three levels of metadata:

1. **Citation Metadata:** any metadata that would be needed for generating a data citation and other general metadata that could be applied to any dataset;
2. **Domain Specific Metadata:** with specific support currently for Social Science, Life Science, Geospatial, and Astronomy datasets;

3. **File-level Metadata:** varies depending on the type of data file.

The Citation Metadata is compliant with DDI Lite (32), DDI 2.5 Codebook (33), DataCite 4.0 (34), and Dublin Core's DCMI Metadata Terms (35) schemas. The default required fields in citation metadata are:

- **Title** for the dataset
- **Author(s)**, with names that can be searched via ORCID IDs
- **Point of Contact** for the dataset, with an email address
- **Description** with some descriptive text
- **Subject** of the dataset, selected from a predefined list

Additional metadata fields include keywords, related publications, notes, depositor (defaulted to the user's account but removable), and deposit date (automatically set to the current date but can also be removed).

Files can be added to a dataset, with a maximum limit of 1000 per dataset. If the instance allows folder uploads, more files can be added by selecting a folder from local storage. The maximum file size limit is 2,5 GB per file. Dataverse also allows a dataset to be saved and published without any files, still issuing a DOI. This is useful if the dataset is stored elsewhere, as a link to it can be provided in the related publication or description metadata field.

In some Dataverse instances, DOI registration can be enabled for each file within a dataset. In this case, each file either receives an independent DOI or a DOI that is an extension of the dataset's DOI but still indexed and cited like a regular one. DOIs are assigned before publication, but they are not indexed until the dataset is published; however, these DOIs can still be used, for example in tags for communication with MEE.

To publish a dataset, the user must submit it for review by the dataverse administrator. Every member of the parent dataverse with permission to publish will be then requested to review and either accept or decline the dataset. Until it is published, the dataset remains in draft form and is visible only to users with permission to view unpublished datasets. This setup also supports further contributions, as users with both view and edit permissions, can add their files and improve the dataset before publication. This feature is particularly useful for research teams, allowing a dataset to be collaboratively built and stored in draft form until the research is complete, at which point it can be submitted for review.

4.3. **Rule-based Data Sharing**

While publishing the data allows the community to access it and conduct further research, it does not directly benefit the initial research from which the data were derived. This is why an incentive-based data sharing approach is needed. In this approach, data are partially published, and to gain access to the full dataset, a user must contribute enough of their own samples that are similar and relevant to the specific research dataset. This approach allows the dataset to grow continually, providing deeper insights and improving research quality.

Implementing such a mechanism on the aforementioned data-sharing repositories is possible thanks to restriction, embargo functionalities, or a role-based access control system. Both types of repositories allow for restricting files in a published record or dataset. In this setup, the dataset's metadata remains publicly visible, but the content cannot be downloaded or opened. Only users specified in the dataset's permissions by its owner or administrator can access the restricted content. On Zenodo, a dataset can only be restricted entirely, while on Dataverse, specific files within a dataset

can be restricted, leaving others publicly accessible. This flexibility allows files like README to be made public, providing information about the restricted content and the policies that allow to access it. However, on Dataverse, all files in a dataset may also be restricted, making only metadata visible without allowing the dataset to be downloaded.

Embargo is another functionality that supports incentive-based data sharing. Similarly to file restriction, an embargo can be placed on a file, but only before publication. To set an embargo, a date must be specified for when this file will automatically become public. On Dataverse, this date cannot be changed after publication, and the embargo cannot be removed, ensuring that data will eventually become accessible to benefit the community. Additionally, on Dataverse, restriction can be combined with embargo, allowing a file to remain restricted even after the embargo expires. Similarly to restriction, an embargo can also be applied to all files in a dataset, making the dataset downloadable only after expiration. On Zenodo, the embargo functionality is more flexible; it can be removed before the set period ends or extended, which is more convenient but depends on users not abusing it. However, Zenodo does not allow embargo and restriction to be combined, as the embargo applies only to restricted files and simply sets an expiration date for the restriction.

To enable these functionalities not only for restricting public access but also for sharing data internally, a role-based sharing mechanism is used. Administrators can assign roles to members of communities on Zenodo and dataverses on Dataverse, granting them specific permissions. By assigning these roles, levels of access to unpublished, restricted, or embargoed files can be set. Additionally, in Dataverse, roles can be assigned to users for specific datasets, allowing them different levels of access to a chosen dataset rather than to all content within the dataverse. Custom roles with tailored combinations of permissions can also be created.

Figure 17: Roles with their permissions available on Dataverse

On Zenodo, roles are assigned only at the community level, and all roles provide access to restricted records within the community. This setup can be used to share internal data among research team members who have a Zenodo community for their team.

Role *

- Reader**
Can view restricted records.
- Curator**
Can curate records and view restricted records.
- Manager**
Can manage members, curate records and view restricted records.
- Owner**
Full administrative access to the entire community.

Figure 18: Roles available on Zenodo

4.3.1. DPValid case rule-based data sharing

The DPValid case was selected for publication on the Sano Dataverse using an incentive-driven, rule-based approach to promote data sharing and foster the creation of a large shared dataset. At the time of publication, the Sano Dataverse was in a test environment (20), so the DOI is not globally indexed or accessible. However, once the production instance (19) is released, the dataset will be republished there, acquiring a valid DOI. The DPValid collection – TKA (36) dataset is published under a CC-BY license, requiring appropriate credit to be given to the original DPValid collection – TKA: “Davico, G., Bottin, F., Labanca, L., Baruffaldi, F., & Viceconti, M. (2024). DPValid collection – TKA (1.0)”.

The dataset is under embargo for 24 months, with restrictions applied to all files except the README.txt. The README file describes the dataset and outlines the policy governing the rule-based approach, including instructions for users who wish to contribute to the dataset. Contributors are required to follow these guidelines:

- **Description and Documentation:** Provide a detailed description of the data to be added to the DPValid collection, along with references to relevant documents, publications, and ethics approval explaining how the data were collected and processed.
- **Relevance:** Ensure the data complements the DPValid collection (e.g., surface EMG and/or dynamometry data recorded during an MVIC test, 3D reconstructions of lower limb muscles, or clinical measures taken on a similar population).
- **Quality Check:** There is no minimum amount of data required for submission, but all contributions will undergo a quality review before access is granted.
- **Sample Submission:** Attach a representative sample of the data to the access request.
- **Data Transfer:** Once approved, transfer the data to the collection owner for integration into the DPValid collection – TKA.

Contributors who provide a suitable data sample and meet quality and relevance criteria will be assigned the File Downloader role. This role restricts editing permissions but allows users to access

and download files before the embargo expires. Once the embargo ends, all files in the dataset will become publicly available, ensuring widespread access.

The DPValid collection – TKA policy is designed to enable continuous expansion of the dataset by the community, benefiting research beyond the project's scope. Scientists are incentivized to contribute their data in exchange for access to the dataset collected during the In Silico World project, increasing its value and encouraging further contributions.

The RODBUK repository will play a key role in disseminating information about the dataset, raising awareness, and facilitating ongoing expansion until the embargo ends.

4.4. RODBUK policies

The RODBUK Cracow Open Research Data Repository (22) project, managed by the Kraków Library Group, unifies Kraków universities and research institutions. It is co-created by six Cracow universities:

- AGH University of Krakow,
- University of Physical Education in Krakow,
- Cracow University of Technology,
- Krakow University of Economics,
- Jagiellonian University in Kraków,
- University of the National Education Commission, Krakow.

RODBUK aggregates all data published on its members' Dataverse instances and indexes it on its own Dataverse instance, increasing visibility and citation potential. RODBUK also provides support in the form of advice on best practices for preparing data for sharing. All data published on RODBUK is stored at ACC Cyfronet (23) and is protected by specific security and backup measures. The repository adheres to OpenAIRE guidelines and follows the FAIR Principles, and is also working towards CoreTrustSeal certification, which requires advanced security and storage policies, such as the obligation to store data for at least 10 years after publication.

Research data can only be deposited by registered individuals who log in through a central authentication system, secured with OIDC (OpenID Connect) (37) or SAML2 (38) protocols. Each login requires an email address and an authentication password (set during the initial login). Depositors have edit rights only within a specific collection. Until the dataset is submitted for verification by the data steward, the depositor can edit the data description and structure. Any further changes to datasets post-submission must be approved by the data steward.

Datasets are published if they contain a mandatory set of metadata and either result from scientific activity, are linked to a publication, or are required by funders/institutional policy on data sharing and long-term preservation. The mandatory set of metadata includes both standard Dataverse requirements and additional fields:

- Descriptive **title** of the dataset (ending without a full stop),
- **Author(s)** with full names or organizational name,
- **Contact** for the dataset with an e-mail address,
- **Description** explaining the purpose, nature, and scope of the dataset,
- **Keywords** in English representing important aspects of the dataset,
- **Branch of Science according to MNiSW** selected from a predefined list

- **Branch of Science according to OECD** selected from a predefined list
- **Language** of the dataset, selected from a predefined list
- **Kind of Data** deposited in the dataset, selected from a predefined list

Additional non-mandatory metadata fields include an alternative language version of the title, contributor information, abstract, related publications or datasets, notes, producer, funding, depositor, and date of collection (start/end). Datasets cannot be published if they present legal and/or ethical issues e.g. infringe any copyright or other intellectual property rights, including but not limited to patents, trademarks, trade secrets, copyrights, rights of publicity or other rights of any third party; data constituting classified information or data protected as a statutory secret, insofar as the use of such data is restricted by law.

Datasets are encoded in Dublin Core, which includes general metadata as well as detailed metadata about variables, dimensions and units used, in a fully machine-readable format. In line with research funding body guidelines, research data should be saved in open formats (e.g. OpenDocument, txt, PNG, FLAC, WebM, HTML, CSS) that are widely available and free of charge, except in cases where file conversion from specialized software to open formats could affect data quality. Files uploaded in both original and open formats should use identical names. The deposited data should be accompanied by a README file containing all the information necessary for further replication and reproducibility of the shared data. A single file cannot be larger than 4 GB. Uploading larger files requires an API token and a script, which is available on GitHub (39). Users who want to upload such a file should contact the Data Steward of their instance in advance. Allowed data compression and archiving programs are ZIP and 7-ZIP. If the data is embargoed, the embargo information must be noted at the file level.

Datasets are stored for at least 10 years, while metadata is stored indefinitely. The technical side of the long-term archiving processes is handled by the ACC Cyfronet AGH team, covering tasks like change of media, conversion to current formats, review of integrity, authenticity, control of availability, reading and presentation of data. These tasks relate to both digital objects and metadata. Long-term data storage is achieved by regularly creating data backups. A backup is made on active data through the replication process from the source location to a separate and isolated target location. The backup procedure ensures the consistency of source and backup data, both at the level of a single file and entire data sets. For obsolete data, their migration/archiving is planned based on solutions using magnetic tape data storage.

ACC Cyfronet AGH guarantees high reliability for data availability. Both hardware and software are well-maintained and tailored to user needs and application functionality. RODBUK operates on virtual machines powered by OpenStack (40), using S3-based object storage, and runs on Rocky Linux 8. The virtual server's physical resources – such as RAM, VCPUs, and disk capacity – are optimized for the application. Due to physical threats that can compromise data integrity, ACC Cyfronet AGH operates in two separate data centres - DC Nawojki and DC Podole - strategically located in different buildings within Krakow. To mitigate the risks associated with natural disasters such as fires or floods, data replication is used. This results in two independent object storage systems, each of which can serve as a failover for the other.

5. Conclusions

The development of integration as well as infrastructure and practices for data-sharing has benefited both the In Silico World project and the broader scientific community both separately and as parts of a general data-sharing framework. The creation of a Zenodo community for ISW has enabled the

curated publication of research results with the ability to cite datasets. The Sano Dataverse instance, an independent, open-source solution aligned with FAIR principles, was developed as an alternative for storing and publishing research data. Although Dataverse offers fewer metadata configuration options than Zenodo, it has more flexible data access policies and provides more possibilities for internal data sharing. As a future part of the RODBUK federation, Sano Dataverse also includes advanced user and data verification policies, ensuring data reliability and enhancing its authority. Data from RODBUK members benefits from advanced security and backup measures, ensuring long-term preservation. The rule-based, incentive-driven approach to data sharing provides a model for supporting research while benefiting the scientific community by sharing some results. This approach can be implemented across various data repositories in different configurations, making it adaptable and accessible. The integration between data repositories and the Model Execution Environment (MEE) platform further supports the research process by enabling direct data flow between HPC infrastructure and data-sharing repositories, which facilitates large-scale simulations with significant volumes of input and output data, allowing for more detailed and informative research.

Together, these solutions create a comprehensive research data management framework for in-silico medical simulations. Input data for model simulations can be published on Dataverse or Zenodo and automatically downloaded and staged as input for MEE computations. When results are generated, they can be automatically uploaded to the ISW Zenodo community, Sano Dataverse, or another instance of the aforementioned repositories. Here, results can be shared privately among research team members to foster collaboration and further study. Additionally, results can be published partially according to the rule-based approach, benefiting from data contributions from the wider scientific community. At the end of the research process, final results can be published with a DOI for citation or attachment to the publication, making them accessible to the scientific community. When published on Sano Dataverse, results are indexed and disseminated through RODBUK, increasing their visibility and ensuring long-term accessibility. Overall, these concepts together provide the scientific community with a powerful and flexible way to manage and share research data, supporting the goals of open science and collaborative research.

Further plans for the development of the framework include ongoing support for existing solutions and analysis of their performance even beyond the scope of the In Silico World project. Since the project helped to establish a collaboration between the partners, it is beneficial to continue and support it. Although technical administration of the Sano Dataverse instance (as part of RODBUK) is handled by ACC Cyfronet AGH, data stewardship responsibilities rest with Sano. These responsibilities include verifying new users, granting access to relevant collections, and reviewing publication requests. Additionally, RODBUK and its members are working toward obtaining CoreTrustSeal (41) certification to ensure the reliability and long-term storage of research data. The DPValid collection, shared under a rule-based data-sharing strategy, requires continuous review of data contributions. In the long term, the growth rate of this collection will be monitored to assess the effectiveness of this sharing approach.

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